

Data Management Plan Checklist

Dataset Overview	
Dataset Title	HCMR Oceanographic buoys Pylos and E1M3a
Dataset Description	Near real time in situ observations in Greek seas
Process Flow Title	
Date of First Version	2021/07/15

Data Collection
What data will you collect or create?
<p>[Questions to consider: - What type, format and volume of data? - Do your chosen formats and software enable sharing and long-term access to the data? - Are there any existing data that you can reuse?]</p> <p>Each platform hosts a number of different sensors recording a variety of parameters (oceanographic, biochemical, meteorological, sound recordings, seismic data, images) with different temporal and spatial coverage. Specifically:</p> <p>Pylos:</p> <p><u>Atmospheric</u> ATMS: Atmospheric pressure at sea level (hPa) DRYT: Air temperature in dry bulb (degrees_C) GDIR: Gust wind from direction relative true north (degree) GSPD: Gust wind speed (m s-1) WDIR: Wind from direction relative true north (degree) WSPD: Horizontal wind speed (m s-1)</p> <p><u>Sea-Temperature</u> TEMP: Sea temperature (degrees_C)</p> <p><u>Salinity-Conductivity</u> PSAL: Practical salinity (0.001)</p> <p><u>Currents</u> HCDT: Current to direction relative true north (degree) HCSP: Horizontal current speed (m s-1)</p> <p><u>Waves</u> VHM0: Spectral significant wave height (Hm0) (m) VMDR: Mean wave direction from (Mdir) (degree) VTM02: Spectral moments (0,2) wave period (Tm02) (s) VTPK: Wave period at spectral peak / peak period (Tp) (s) VZMX: Maximum zero crossing wave height (Hmax) (m)</p> <p><u>Optical</u> TUR4: Turbidity (1)</p> <p><u>Biochemical</u> DOX1: Dissolved oxygen (ml l-1) FLU2: Chlorophyll-a fluorescence (mg m-3)</p>

Pylos Platform

Supersensitive pressure sensor data to detect tsunami waves

Ambient sound recordings

Seismographic (OBS)

Gravimeter data

Lighting system data

Picture and Video recording system data

E1M3A

Atmospheric

ATMS: Atmospheric pressure at sea level (hPa)

DRYT: Air temperature in dry bulb (degrees_C)

GDIR: Gust wind from direction relative true north (degree)

GSPD: Gust wind speed (m s-1)

WDIR: Wind from direction relative true north (degree)

WSPD: Horizontal wind speed (m s-1)

Sea-Temperature

TEMP: Sea temperature (degrees_C)

Salinity-Conductivity

PSAL: Practical salinity (0.001)

Currents

HCDT: Current to direction relative true north (degree)

HCSP: Horizontal current speed (m s-1)

Waves

VHM0: Spectral significant wave height (Hm0) (m)

VMDR: Mean wave direction from (Mdir) (degree)

VTM02: Spectral moments (0,2) wave period (Tm02) (s)

VTPK: Wave period at spectral peak / peak period (Tp) (s)

VZMX: Maximum zero crossing wave height (Hmax) (m)

Optical

TUR4: Turbidity (1)

Biochemical

DOX1: Dissolved oxygen (ml l-1)

FLU2: Chlorophyll-a fluorescence (mg m-3)

PHPH: Ph (1)

All the collected datasets are either transmitted in real time to POSEIDON operational data center through satellite and mobile networks or saved into attached data loggers / storage media for later retrieval and processing. The raw data (as provided by the sensors) are undergoing a first level of metadata processing and homogenization following certain naming, units and date format conventions and are then stored into a specifically developed database system. Apart from the instantly recorded parameters, a number of derived parameters (salinity, dissolved oxygen, sound velocity, etc) are also included in the available observations.

How will the data be collected or created?

[Questions to Consider: - What standards or methodologies will you use? - How will you structure and name your folders and files? - How will you handle versioning? - What quality assurance processes will you adopt?]

The conventions and the list of the parameters metadata used in the implementation of all the provided measurements are part of the Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC - physical parameters list.

- [Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC - physical parameters](#)

After the homogenization process is complete, a first level of quality control is applied on the measurements with the use of automated near real time procedures (NRT qc). These procedures provide a first evaluation of the quality of the data by taking into consideration minimum and maximum valid ranges, spikes and stuck values. The initial values of the datasets are not changed but an additional flag depicting the quality is included as a descriptor to each value. Apart from the automated near real time quality control, a delayed mode quality control is applied using advanced procedures, data comparison and visual inspection conducted by experienced scientists on a later time and at least twice per year. All these procedures are defined by parameter, elaborated in coherence with international agreements, in particular those adopted within SeaDataNet project. Detailed information on the applied procedures can be found in the Relative Documentation on the CMEMS In Situ QC procedure manuals.

Near Real Time Quality Control procedures

- [International quality control agreements adopted within SeaDataNet project](#)

CMEMS In Situ TAC QC procedure manuals for:

- [Temperature and Salinity, Currents and Sea Level,](#)
- [Waves,](#)
- [Chlorophyll-A, Dissolved Oxygen and Nutrients](#)

As soon as an evaluation phase is complete, the data and metadata are formatted into netCDF (Network Common Data Form) files, following globally used format conventions and standards by OceanSites and Copernicus.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

[Questions to consider: - What information is needed for the data to be to be read and interpreted in the future? - How will you capture / create this documentation and metadata? - What metadata standards will you use and why?]

The data and metadata are formatted into netCDF (Network Common Data Form) files, following globally used format conventions and standards by OceanSites and Copernicus.

Format Information

- [Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC - physical parameters](#)
- [Copernicus Marine In Situ NetCDF format manual](#)

Standards that the above documentation is based on:

- ☞ <http://cfconventions.org/>
- ☞ <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/udunits/>
- ☞ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_8601

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

[Questions to consider: - Have you gained consent for data preservation and sharing? - How will you protect the identity of participants if required? E.g. via anonymisation - How will sensitive data be handled to ensure it is stored and transferred securely?]

Data are product of HCMR. No sensitive data are provided

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

[Questions to consider: - Who owns the data? - How will the data be licensed for reuse? - Are there any restrictions on the reuse of third-party data? - Will data sharing be postponed / restricted e.g. to publish or seek patents?]

Distribution statement: "These data follow the standards of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (<http://marine.copernicus.eu>); they are public and free of charge. User assumes all risk for use of data. User must display citation in any publication or product using data. User must contact PI prior to any commercial use of data."

Citation: "These data were collected and made freely available by the POSEIDON system (<https://poseidon.hcmr.gr>) operated by the Institute of Oceanography of HCMR"

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

[Questions to consider: - Do you have sufficient storage or will you need to include charges for additional services? - How will the data be backed up? - Who will be responsible for backup and recovery? - How will the data be recovered in the event of an incident?]

The operational center of POSEIDON is located at HCMR's facilities in Anavyssos, Attica. It consists of a cluster of servers and storage media which provides cloud services of high availability and load distribution with the use of a series of virtual machines together with High Performance Computers capable to support the timely provision of the POSEIDON forecasting products and the Copernicus Marine's wave forecasts for the Mediterranean.

The POSEIDON HPC system includes:

- One SGI Altix UV2000 cluster with 208 cores Intel Xeon E5-4650 @ 2.60GHz and 768 GB RAM
- One HP DL360 Gen10 with 24 cores Intel Xeon Gold 6126 CPU @ 2.60GHz and 512 GB RAM
- A dedicated 150TB storage system for the forecasting models needs

For the required data processing and analysis, the development and support of the POSEIDON services as well as for the linking with the Distribution Units (DUs) of Copernicus Marine Service, more than 18 Virtual Machines (VMs) have been created on 4 physical servers with a total number of 128 cores and 768GB RAM, supported by a data storage system with full capacity of 50TB. The servers, the storage media and the network devices are connected through multiple and high speed links in order to achieve the highest availability and fastest response time for the hosted services.

All the POSEIDON servers are running on community-driven free operating systems, while all the POSEIDON services and the dissemination tools are built on open source software.

How will you manage access and security?

[Questions to consider: - What are the risks to data security and how will these be managed? - How will you control access to keep the data secure? - How will you ensure that collaborators can access your data securely? - If creating or collecting data in the field how will you ensure its safe transfer into your main secured systems?]

All the collected datasets are either transmitted in real time to POSEIDON operational data center through satellite and mobile networks or saved into attached data loggers / storage media for later retrieval and processing.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

[Questions to consider: - What data must be retained/destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes? - How will you decide what other data to keep? - What are the foreseeable research uses for the data? - How long will the data be retained and preserved?]

Long term preservation.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

[Questions to consider: - Where e.g. in which repository or archive will the data be held? - What costs if any will your selected data repository or archive charge? - Have you costed in time and effort to prepare the data for sharing / preservation?]

The data are stored into RDBMS (PostgreSQL) and the access to the data is provided through a Restful API using Auth0 authentication method. The initial raw data are also stored in ascii format (txt, csv files)

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

[Questions to consider: - How will potential users find out about your data? - With whom will you share the data, and under what conditions? - Will you share data via a repository, handle requests directly or use another mechanism? - When will you make the data available? - Will you pursue getting a persistent identifier for your data?]

The NetCDF files are distributed into some of the most known repositories for marine data such as Copernicus and EMODnet.

Apart from these repositories, the available datasets are publicly accessible through the POSEIDON services as open data. The users can view a brief graphical presentation of the POSEIDON network of observatories and the recorded data, as well as download the datasets of interest. The access to the download services is free but restricted to registered users.

<https://poseidon.hcmr.gr/services/ocean-data>

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

[Questions to consider: - What action will you take to overcome or minimise restrictions? - For how long do you need exclusive use of the data and why? - Will a data sharing agreement (or equivalent) be required?]

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Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

[Questions to consider: - Who is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised? - Who will be responsible for each data management activity? - How will responsibilities be split across partner sites in collaborative research projects? - Will data ownership and responsibilities for RDM be part of any consortium agreement or contract agreed between partners?]

responsible for DMP implementation and responsibilities for RDM: PI of POSEIDON System (Leonidas Perivoliotis)

review, revision and further data management activities : Head of POSEIDON IT team (Maria Sotiropoulou)

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

[Questions to consider: - Is additional specialist expertise (or training for existing staff) required? - Do you require hardware or software which is additional or exceptional to existing institutional provision? - Will charges be applied by data repositories?]

Currently the POSEIDON IT team holds the required expertise for the implementation of the DMP. The existing institutional resources can sustainably support the DMP implementation as it is described in this document.